

Net Zero City Complexity, a Study of Emerging Trends from Net Zero Cities

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Abstract

Australian cities can achieve net zero goals by emulating global best practices and lessons learnt from others focused on collaboration, iterative learning, accessibility, innovation, and affordability. Cities should adopt inclusive governance connecting government, industry, and communities to enable systemic change. Successful cities adopt a collaborative governance approach across government, private sector, and local communities to enable systemic change; both top down (Calgary and Edmonton) and bottom up (Melbourne), as well as exploring regional partnerships (Under2 Coalition) driving shared sustainability outcomes when facing similar climate challenges translating to local solutions. The cities take an iterative approach to policy development, leveraging data and predictive modelling to track progress and amplify success stories and Indigenous knowledge to diverse audiences. Industry coordination drives technological and supply chain solutions to shared challenges, facilitated by making a business case for adaptation (Germany and Denmark) and offering innovative financing (Japan and Zimbabwe). Overall, inclusive processes that enable markets and diffuse technologies in an affordable way underpin climate progress in leading cities working towards ambitious emissions goals.

In addition to sectoral impact, the theoretical application in this research is weighted to ensure a systems theory approach will impact long-term effective net-zero transition and effect a framework of sustainable solutions. A system of systems methodology ensures a collective application of both transitional and circular systemic theories which are necessary to underpin carbon neutral urban design. This will be effective with additional emphasis being placed on socio-ecological and sociotechnical systems. The combined systems theory approach provides a holistic framework which operates at a macro-level, hierarchical function of interconnected structures. This research has qualitatively determined which pathways of governance and adaptation have potential to realise success and will enable corrective planning and define the methodology of future design and developments of net zero cities.

1. Introduction and Overview

The UN Climate Change Conference (COP21), hosted in Paris in December 2015, referred to as the Paris agreement which created a multilateral platform and global impetus to mitigate greenhouse gas reductions and collectively achieve climate-neutrality. 196 Parties adopted the legally binding international treaty on climate change, with the objective to limit global warming to below the 1.5°C with an emission reduction target of 45% by 2030 below 2005 levels (Popovski and Popovski 2018).

The methodology underpinning this agreement is through nationally determined contributions (NDC), national action plans developed country by country to target and mitigate climate change and related impacts. The NDCs have a five-year cyclical adjustment period requiring stepped increase to targets and action plans. For countries to achieve their NDC and collectively reduce emissions to 45%

pre 2005 levels there have been a range of mitigation sectoral structured strategies (Popovski and Popovski 2018).

56% of the global population estimated at ~9 billion people currently reside in urban spaces or cities, with projections to increase to 68% by 2050 (The World Bank 2020). Urban environments are the primary areas of economic growth, generating an estimated ~80% of global gross domestic product yet are responsible for the consumption of 85% of global resources 85% and are simultaneously responsible for the accumulative output of ~70% of global emissions (Huovila et al. 2022).

Carbon neutral or net zero cities (NZC) are one of the mitigation strategies that are considered critical in helping achieve the 2030 target (Duan and Kim 2023). A NZC is defined as an urban environment realising a net amount of zero emissions through strategies that have a carbon-neutral outcome where the net greenhouse gas emissions associated with a city are zero (Huovila et al. 2022).

Local governments are the central to climate governance and have been identified to be directly and indirectly responsible for the percentage of GHG emitted from their local areas. Consistency is difficult to quantify considering the variations in density, area, sectoral impacts and influences. These differences compound the difficulties in devising consistent frameworks for carbon neutral urban environments. This complexity is highlighted through the systemic adaptation and recommendation presented in this proposal. These solutions have been assessed through a multidisciplinary approach in order to bridge the knowledge gap evidenced in the lack or failure from local decarbonization policy and technical applications.

Best practices are evidenced from the following cities, Calgary, Edmonton and Melbourne. Additional drivers that facilitate nationwide systemic change are explored in Germany, Denmark, Japan, Zimbabwe and Korea. These country examples provide further insights and learning where comparative data and emerging patterns present alongside impacts resulting from population density, culture and socio-economic considerations. Each urban area presents variable circumstances, demographics and typography, which together have resulted in assorted decarbonization strategies (Linton, Clarke and Tozer 2022).

There are key areas that have taken priority in decarbonization. These are listed but not limited to energy, mobility, waste, buildings, water, green and food. While these areas are responsible for the majority of carbon related emissions, mitigation in these industries alone are not sufficient to ensure a carbon neutral environment. Additional complexities and considerations are necessary for adaptation and these need to include emerging technologies in GHG mitigation and adaptive measures to decrease related scope 3 emission levels¹.

Document scope

¹ Scope 3 emissions are defined by the Australian Government Clean Energy Regulator as indirect greenhouse gas emissions that are generated in the wider economy and that occur as a consequence of the activities of a facility, but from sources not owned or controlled by that facility's business.

A systematic database search and baseline rapid review forms the base of this research and facilitates inclusion of applicable literature and documents to support the systems theory approach that will be included in this research proposal. We will discuss below the underpinning theoretical frames and empirical methods suitable for determining mitigation strategies of carbon neutral urban environments. This discussion will be useful for adapting leading global knowledge and designing a contextually relevant net zero city framework for Australia.

Search strings and database selection

An initial examination of net zero literature included the wording “ Net Zero”, “Net Zero Cities”, “Net zero City”, “Carbon Neutral” “Systems Theory” and “Decarbonization”. Using the variable of AND presented limited search results, especially when isolating the search criteria in Title, Key Words and Abstract.

Trial searches were conducted and repeated with variations, exclusions and adaptations on wording until the search strings were developed (Table 1). The combination of “AND” yielded a smaller range of articles, but limitations to title only produced very few results, regardless of the database. Resultant searches were broader to allow for title, abstract and keywords to be included in the search string.

This string was run in Scopus and Proquest, which allowed for broad search parameters due to these databases containing a broad range of multi-disciplinary journal articles. The included articles were limited to English only journal publications, published after 2019. Due to the multidisciplinary research application of this paper, additional resources out of scope of the database search will be included in citations.

Defining the search string required a multifaceted approach as the initial results and variable strings yielded a broader range of immaterial articles, both in terms of the results being more specific in subject matter and not producing a broader scale of representational literature. Additional complexities presented in combining search words which limited the criteria and the generated results presented in literature gaps and fewer publications, that were more targeted although limited in number.

As a conceptual analysis, the preliminary search criteria was based on commonality of search terms but were limited to qualitative and quantitative metrics subject choice in relation to developing and designing systems to be applied for the design of net zero cities (see table 2). Further due diligence will ensure the legitimacy of the results by analysing the abstracts and journal content in more detail

Table 1: Concept grid: keywords with a primary word listing.

	Key words	Associated terms or words
		Key terms or words used in search string
Principle criterion	Net Zero Cities	carbon neutrality, net-zero, circular economy, doughnut economics, 2030 targets, Paris Agreement, Urban, carbon neutral, low emissions,

		net zero emissions, negative emissions, low carbon, renewable, green, environment, waste recycle, solutions, cradle to grave, urban metabolism, linear, circularity, green cities, sustainable cities "carbon neutrality" AND "net-zero" AND "net zero" "Net Zero Cities" AND "Net Zero City" AND "Net" AND "Zero" and city*
	Systems Theory	System theory, framework, application, approach, methodology, systemic, multidisciplinary, transformative, Systems of system, Social technical systems theory, Social ecological systems theory Stockholm resilience centre, Eleanor Olstrom, Doughnut Economics theory, Transition towns, "Systems Theory " AND "System Theory " AND System*
	Decarbonization	Emission reduction, renewable, energy, GHG emissions, carbon, carbon neutral, remove carbon, decarbonise, sustainable, " decarbonization " OR "carbon neutral" OR "emission reduction"

Table 2: List of search strings with name and key words, limitation include a date range 2019-2023

Name	Search String
Scopus_SSA	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Net Zero City" OR nzc OR "Net Zero Cities") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (decarbonization*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("system" AND "theory"))
Scopus_SSB	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Net Zero") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (city*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("systems off system"))
Scopus_SSC	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Net Zero City" OR "Net Zero Cities"))
Scopus_SSD	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Net Zero") AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (city*) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (decarbonization)))
Scopus_SSE	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Net Zero") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (city*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (system*))
ProQuest_SSA	noft("net zero cities" OR "net zero city") OR noft("net zero") AND abstract(system*) AND abstract(theory*)
ProQuest_SSB	noft("net zero cities" OR "net zero city" OR NZC*) OR noft("sustainable cities" OR "green cities") AND noft(system*)

Theoretical underpinnings of Net Zero City discourse

Considerations related to the following theories have been explored through a theoretical systems approach and database literature review to assist in defining and applying an adaptive design of NZC. These include but are not limited to Doughnut economics, U.N 2.0 six transitions, system-of-systems thinking, socio-ecological systems and sociotechnical systems, circular metabolic urban landscapes and NZC's and pathways to interconnected city environments.

System-of-systems thinking

Though it is often energy sector-centric in its public framing, the theoretical underpinnings of the contemporary Net Zero City (NZC) research and development (R&D) agenda have been informed by the discourses of both energy transitions, which may or may not include sustainability and fairness as explicit aims, and sustainability transitions which go beyond energy to include for example water, food, and materials (Araújo, 2023). At their core, NZC projects employ systems-of-systems SoS thinking. SoS is characterised by a collection of systems designed to execute specific functions or capabilities, incorporating at least one function or capability that cannot be accomplished by an individual system alone. By applying a "systems of systems" approach, urban planners have a methodological tool for identifying interdependencies and designing holistic solutions. For example, integrating renewable energy systems with regenerative agriculture and smart transportation infrastructure would require a comprehensive understanding of how each of these systems interact to effectively approach carbon neutrality across the three systems. SoS thinking recognises both socio-ecological systems and sociotechnical systems and thus employs an interdisciplinary range of human ecology and environmental science perspectives.

Socio-ecological systems and sociotechnical systems

Socio-ecological systems (SES) serve as a conceptual framework operating at a meta-level, conceptualising hierarchies of interrelated systems with variables influencing outcomes. SES is designed to examine the intricate connections between social and environmental factors and their collective impact on achieving sustainability goals across diverse systems, levels, and scales. Originally rooted in the concepts of collective action, this framework has evolved into a widely referenced tool for assessing sustainability within social-ecological systems (Partelow, 2018). A related meta-level framework is that associated with sociotechnical systems (STS). This conceptual framework also allows for nested system hierarchies, highlighting coevolution and multidimensional interactions, such as those between industry, technology, markets, policy culture, and civil society (Geels, 2012).

In contrast to SES, the STS framework primarily focuses on the interconnected linkages and interactions between society and technology, operating across diverse systems, levels, and scales. When applied to energy-specific STS, particularly in areas such as electricity, heating, and mobility, the analysis extends to internal processes, innovations, and activities. STS theorises that these factors can induce changes within the system entities and alter the relationships between them.

STS and SES are prevalent in the Sustainable Urban Development (SUD) discourse as they relate to the social settings and pre-conditions of effective NZC implementation. In theoretical conversation with NZC discourse, two key examples of the empirical application of SES and STS respectively, include:

- Sustainable cities and green nature spaces: The idea of green cities can be traced back to at least the storied hanging gardens of Babylon and their purported large-scale engineering and integration of water system technology and nature into metropolitan spaces (Dalley, 2013). Whether or not historically accurate, these gardens represent a clear and enduring civic imaginary with implications for increased socio-ecological health and wellbeing; food,

medicine, timber, and fiber security (depending on what is growing in the garden); and civic pride. Today, the theoretical underpinning of green cities (re)introduces the inclusion of natural, biophilic design elements and the crucial role of water stewardship into the cityscape, along with climate change mitigation and adaptation, land use management practices and infrastructure (Etingoff, 2017; Zhou; 2013).

- Smart and intelligent cities: The concept of smart and intelligent cities can be traced back to at least the 1980's sociotechnical imaginary of the technopolis and the transformation of traditional cities into a global network city of dispersed, highly interactive economic nodes connected through extensive networks of airports, highways, and communications technology (Glasmeier, A., & Christopherson, S. 2015). Since then, and in line with socio-cultural trends, the smart cities discourse and rhetorical narrative has shifted towards a technology-driven approach to human-centric social innovation in civic spaces; and seeks to understand the impact that information technology can have on the urban fabric and norms of behaviour Lytras and Visvizi, 2020). In many cases, the public response to smart cities planning and development communications has been met with resistance as a "strategy for discipline" (Vanolo, 2014).

Circular metabolic urban landscapes

Systemic adaptive methodology considers the linear input and output of current urban metabolisms and requires a systems theory approach in order to adapt to a more circularity model, which in turn will enhance a lower emission or zero emission output (Newton et al. 2019; Zhang 2023). The SES and STS theoretical frames discussed above, when combined and applied to cities, may produce Amenta et. al. (2022) describe as a circular metabolic urban landscape, a constantly transforming living organism that integrates the circular city model and the urban metabolism model. The circular metabolic urban landscape is theorised to apply "a closure of production processes through looping actions, by improving and connecting supply chains, re-cycling avoidable waste and transforming them into new resources" in a way that embraces "the need for the regeneration of depleted territories". Drawing on the circular economic concept seeking to mimic the zero-waste outputs found in natural systems, the circular city model suggests that the economy should replicate the functioning of natural ecosystems, wherein the symbiotic functioning of these systems prevent the generation of waste from the design and outset of the systems operations. This interpretation contrasts in intent and principle with a somewhat diminished concept of circular economy that is driven mechanically by the question of how to recycle all the waste a human system produces into ever more productive systems (Popp et al, 2022).

Figure 1 (Novotny 2011) Contrasting models showing a linear vs circular urban metabolism

The circular metabolic urban landscape model recognises that closing resource loops of production cycles alone is insufficient; that effective circular metabolic resource management involves equilibrium between “citizens well-being, urban structure and the natural environment from which it draws (often non-renewable) resources, materials and energy” (2022). Amenta et. al. call for a systemic approach that employs a diversity of skills and disciplines such as from human ecology of social sciences, industrial ecology and Material Flow Analysis, urban political ecology, and Landscape Ecology.

An enabling urban systems transformation framework is key to transformative change in urban environments, alternating between voices or recommendations that guide processes from design, to engagement to partnerships leading to knowledge sharing and application. Multidisciplinary research and systems thinking approach will ensure a fit for purpose model, co-designed to be adaptive across multiple place-based locations (Webb et al. 2023). This paper will further explore the fundamentals and enabling structures required for recommendation, adaptation, implementation.

Figure 2 (Webb et al. 2023) Categorical process showing an enabling urban systems transformation framework.

Doughnut economics theory

Kate Raworth's theory and model, doughnut economics, emphasises a balance between social foundations and environmental boundaries. Applying this theory to a net-zero cities framework involves ensuring that urban development meets the needs of all within the means of the planet. This requires integrating sustainable practices, prioritizing social well-being, and minimizing environmental impact with a focus on fluctuating production and consumption to create resilient, equitable net-zero cities (Raworth 2017).

Key focus points from a theory approach are decarbonisation, the energy transition, circular economy, digitalisation, urban design, social equity and biodiversity.

Figure 3 (Raworth 2017) “Exploring Doughnut Economics” diagram and indicative system boundaries

SDG six transitions

This methodology of six transitions has synergies with systemic design of NZC and is aligned to increase and impact sustainable environments. These are a convergence of accelerators and enablers with transformative entry points that have been developed to compound and multiple impacts across the SDGs. These include a systemic approach to food systems; energy access and affordability; digital connectivity; education; jobs and social protection; climate change; biodiversity loss and pollution (United Nations 2023).

Although not an innovative concept, this systems approach is an adaptive organisational framework that transforms current policies and adapts pathways to help accelerate the 2030 Agenda across urban environments. Prioritising above all the health and wellbeing of citizens and natural environments through interconnected, interdisciplinary systems represents a critical component of leading NZC scholarship and practice.

Figure 4 (UNCTAD 2023) mapping based on six transition pathway

NZC's and pathways to interconnected city environments

It has long been recognised that “municipalities that might wish to act in a globally solidary way [...] by reducing their carbon dioxide emissions, may see such efforts as useless as long as they cannot trust that other municipalities will also do their part to reduce emissions” (Næss, 2001). In addition, a city cannot achieve net-zero carbon emissions by solely focusing on sequestering carbon emissions from within its administrative boundaries. Because of carbon lock-in, and the complex interplay between urban infrastructure and human behavior, a strategic approach to mitigation is essential for cities to achieve net-zero carbon emissions (Seto et. al., 2021). In this spirit, the International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives (ICLEI) has been established, which includes at least 535 cities around the world including Sydney, Melbourne and 5 other cities in Australia, that have now made formal commitments to climate / carbon neutrality. The measurement of these commitments and their approaches vary by city environment and context, however, the ICLEI has established 5 pathways to SUD (https://iclei.org/our_approach/). These are:

Low Emission Development Pathway:

- A strategy to combat climate change by reducing pollutants, achieving climate neutrality, and promoting sustainable mobility options, creating economic opportunities.

Nature-Based Development Pathway:

- Focuses on protecting biodiversity and ecosystems in and around cities, emphasising blue and green infrastructure, and incorporating nature into economic opportunities.

Equitable and People-Centered Development Pathway:

- Prioritises just, inclusive urban communities by addressing systemic inequalities, improving livability, safety, and human health, and ensuring equitable access to essential resources.

Resilient Development Pathway:

- Anticipates and responds to shocks and stresses, integrating resilience into municipal strategies, and strengthening essential systems in a transparent and inclusive manner.

Circular Development Pathway:

- Aims to create closed-loop systems in urban environments, minimising waste, promoting sustainable consumption, and aligning with the principles of a circular economy.

Each of the five pathways are theorised as essential and integral to developing sustainable cities, the low emission development pathway holds significant relevance to industry sector inputs and outputs that may be leveraged towards achieving NZC outcomes. The key provisioning systems - or sectors - that influence NZC outcomes require the design of community-wide integrated urban infrastructure transitions relevant to both production and consumption patterns, including in; energy, mobility, buildings, water, waste/sewage management, green infrastructure and food systems (Tong et. al., 2021). An effective approach to achieving NZC emission targets will include transitional objectives, strategies and integration considerations for each of these provisioning systems. Below is a summary of these provisioning systems, and examples of objectives, strategies and integration considerations, as they relate to system-wide transitions.

Energy Transition:

- Objective: Shift towards decreased energy consumption, and sustainable and renewable energy sources.
- Strategies: Implement solar, wind, biodigester and/or other clean energy solutions as relevant to context; promote decrease in energy and energy consumption across sectors, and increased energy efficiency.
- Integration: Ensure cyclical coordination between energy production, distribution, consumption.

Mobility Transition:

- Objective: Foster sustainable, efficient and active urban mobility.
- Strategies: Prioritise walking, cycling, and public transit; promote shared mobility options; encourage the electrification of vehicle fleets and private use of electric vehicles.
- Integration: Develop and/or modify interconnected active and non-active transportation systems to minimise environmental impact and enhance accessibility.

Buildings Transition:

- Objective: Achieve energy-efficient, sustainable, and resilient structures.
- Strategies: Prioritise biophilic design and net-zero energy buildings, green construction materials, and energy-efficient retrofits.
- Integration: Integrate building designs with reticulated energy, water and human waste efficiency measures.

Water Transition:

- Objective: Ensure efficient water use and sustainable water management.
- Strategies: Design reticulated water-saving technologies, promote water conservation, and invest in sustainable wastewater treatment including stormwater, grey and black waters.
- Integration: Align water management strategies with broader system inputs and resource reticulation planning to optimise water resources.

Waste/Sewage Management Transition:

- Objective: Minimise waste and optimise waste management practices.
- Strategies: Encourage waste reduction, recycling, and circular/metabolic economy principles; implement efficient sewage treatment systems.
- Integration: Coordinate waste management efforts with other urban systems inputs to reduce negative environmental impact and increase sustainability gains.

Green Infrastructure Transition:

- Objective: Enhance urban green spaces and biodiversity.
- Strategies: Implement biophilic design and engineering of green roofs, urban parks, and green corridors; prioritise blue and green infrastructure connections wherever possible and practical
- Integration: Integrate green spaces seamlessly into urban planning to enhance and optimise ecosystem service delivery and overall environmental quality.

Food Systems Transition:

- Objective: Promote sustainable and localised/regionalised food production and consumption systems.
- Strategies: Encourage urban agriculture, reduce food waste, and support local food production; integrate regenerative practices into the food supply chain in ways designed to enhance local/regional food security and economic development.
- Integration: Align food systems with broader sustainability, health and local economic development goals, connecting agriculture with waste management, water management, transport and green spaces.

2. Implementation

The Challenge in Achieving Net Zero Transition

Achieving net zero emissions represents an unprecedented economic and social transformation entailing complex political, financial, cultural, and technical hurdles. As stated by the (World Economic Forum 2021), to deliver net zero carbon cities it is essential that city and national governments, business and civil society align and collaborate on a common agenda. However;

1. Politically, governments lack consistent long-term commitments, with policy and regulatory barriers hindering clean technology adoption and insufficient collaboration hampering global progress.
2. Economically, transitions face massive underinvestment, with funding unavailable for countries and companies to unravel from carbon-intensive assets, threatening jobs and competitiveness.
3. Societally, public scepticism and entitlement to high-emission lifestyles preserves cultural dependence on fossil fuels, while low-income groups disproportionately bear transition costs.
4. Technologically, difficulties rapidly scaling emerging innovations to infrastructure levels needed for whole-system decarbonisation are compounded by existing grid, building, and transport asset inertia.

Investing in standalone technical solutions will not be enough to overcome these deep structural challenges that instead requires balancing holistic political, financial, and social priorities in service of equitable clean energy transition. But the complexity of fundamentally reshaping economic systems and societal norms means transitions cannot occur without inclusive, deep collaboration benefiting those most economically vulnerable.

Achieving net zero thus demands a web of multilateral support and participation stretching across government, industry, research and community levels worldwide for integrated action reducing emissions and creating a place that recognisably meets the needs of people and strengthens quality of life. Although extending ambition through one approach will create opportunities in other areas, considering the ten approaches (shown in Figure 5) together will help to ensure that they are delivered in ways that 'do no significant harm', and that one environmental objective is not achieved at the expense of another.

Figure 5 : Global best-practice approaches (Chartier, Frost & Pountney 2021)

Opportunity Areas in Net Zero Transition

The pathways developed by the case cities generally resemble each other with targets/goals, actions and indicators to measure progress. Accordingly, five main priority sectors for decarbonisation can be identified as: energy (mainly electricity), buildings (existing and new), transportation, waste and carbon. These sectors represent the vast majority of city-wide emissions and local governments have a degree of control and/or jurisdiction over them (Alliance 2015; Linton, Clarke & Tozer 2022; Robinson & Gore 2005).

Table 3 Empirical: evidence and literature comparison (Linton, Clarke & Tozer 2022)

Sector	Literature	Empirical
Electricity	Cities can utilise building scale and district energy solutions if they do not have full control over energy	All of the cases have made ambitious targets to decarbonise the electricity sector. Smaller cities tend to prioritise renewable energy generation.

Existing Buildings	Retrofits are necessary to improve energy efficiency and heating/ cooling systems must be converted to zero emissions systems.	Local governments are leading by example and retrofitting corporate owned buildings. They are also developing programs to educate and incentivise privately building owners to retrofit.
New Buildings	Low or zero carbon emissions standards for new buildings	Local governments are implementing voluntary building codes, and in some cases mandatory ones.
Fuel shift	Local governments have little control other than the vehicles directly owned by the City. They can create incentives and use market based instruments (MBIs) to influence residents to use zero emissions vehicles.	All the cases are investing in electric public transit and EV charging stations throughout the cities.
Mode shift	Mode shift can be influenced through active transportation and public transit infrastructure investments and MBIs	All of the cases are investing in better pedestrian and bike infrastructure. Some cases are developing incentives to use walk, bike or use public transit, some cases are implementing regulations to reduce traffic in certain areas.
Waste	Cities can reduce emissions in this sector by diverting waste from landfills or incineration by providing better services and/or enabling activities. Waste-to-energy infrastructure and landfill gas capture systems can also be built to limit emissions from this sector.	Not all cities have direct control over waste management. Those that do are increasing diversion rates and installing gas capture and waste-to-energy systems.
Carbon Sinks and Offsets	Local governments can purchase carbon offsets and/or increase the capacity of local carbon sinks	Most of the cases include carbon-offsetting strategies to meet their GHG reduction targets.

While these approaches can help move cities towards a net zero carbon future, integrated solutions will result in greater impact (World Economic Forum 2021). Detailed strategies have been evaluated for 6 countries at different stages of development, including Canada, Denmark, Germany and South Korea, as well as emerging cities like Zimbabwe, which is outlined in the following case studies.

Key Insights from Case Studies

Australian cities aiming to achieve net zero targets can look to global best practices and lessons learnt that emphasise deep collaboration, continual learning, accessibility, innovation, and affordability. Successful cities adopt a collaborative governance approach across government, private sector, and local communities to break down silos. They take an iterative approach to policy development, leveraging data and predictive modelling to track progress and amplify success stories. Information and practical guidance on reducing emissions is translated for diverse audiences and tailored for key groups like businesses and educators. Industry coordination drives technological and supply chain solutions to shared challenges, facilitated by making a business case for adaptation and offering innovative financing. Overall, inclusive processes that enable markets and diffuse technologies in an affordable way underpin climate progress in leading cities working towards ambitious emissions goals.

<i>Key Insights</i>	<i>Takeaway</i>
<i>(1) Deep Collaboration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Better coordination between all stakeholders - private sector, governments, communities ● Adopt collaborative approaches that are inclusive and tap into diverse knowledge ● Break down governance and professional silos that hinder joint working
<i>(2) Continual Learning and Improvement</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Take an iterative approach with monitoring, evaluation and updating ● Build on local knowledge, data and predictive modelling to track progress ● Amplify success stories and share lessons learned

<p><i>(3) Accessible Information</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Translate materials for diverse audiences and equity-deserving groups ● Curate and share practical resources, tools and market information ● Develop tailored guidance for key audiences like business sectors and educators
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Melbourne

Regen Melbourne is a community-focused sustainability and climate resilience initiative launched in 2019 by the Lord Mayor’s Charitable Foundation, a leading philanthropic organisation in Melbourne. The overarching objectives are to accelerate Melbourne’s transition towards becoming a sustainable, resilient and carbon neutral city by 2030. This involves coordinated climate action across areas like the built environment, transport systems, food systems and natural landscapes within the city.

The initiative follows a community-driven systems change model centred on collective impact rather than being structured as top-down centralised planning by the city government. It aims to leverage capabilities from a diverse range of stakeholders spanning government bodies, businesses, academic institutions, technology startups, Indigenous groups, and grassroots community organisations. The strategic direction and governance are provided by a Leadership Council with members drawn from various partner entities.

Key focus areas for the Regen Melbourne initiative cover regenerating waterways, green infrastructure and landscapes, local food systems and urban agriculture practices, measuring what matters (doughnut model), and advances towards a circular economy.

Canada

The city of Calgary instead used a top-down planning approach led by the city government, which provides a framework for coordinated municipal action on climate resilience through evidence-based risk analysis and preparedness across city services.

Calgary developed a comprehensive climate resilience strategy in 2018 to assess climate-related risks across its services and operations and devise targeted adaptation actions to build preparedness. This plan was formulated as part of Calgary's commitment to the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, which brought together local and regional governments globally to pledge climate mitigation and adaptation goals in line with Paris Agreement targets.

The resilience plan involved undertaking evidence-based climate risk assessments of potential hazards like flooding, droughts, extreme heat and mapping the vulnerabilities of city infrastructure,

buildings, utilities, transit networks etc. Exposure analysis estimated potential economic losses and damages along with costs to public safety from climate disruptions. This informed the framework devised with priority areas identified, timeline defined, and departmental roles and responsibilities assigned. Specific resilience initiatives and investments were formulated covering stormwater management, transportation infrastructure, facilities, parks, public health precautions targeted for city delivery units. There was also emphasis on supporting climate-vulnerable neighborhoods, and ensuring equitable resilience outcomes.

Oversight for plan implementation involves an interdepartmental climate resilience team working alongside regional partners. Progress is tracked based on risk reduction metrics and indicators like increased green space cover as well as embodied carbon savings in infrastructure. The evidence-based and coordinated city-wide adaptation approach has helped inform Calgary's policies, infrastructure upgrades, and community programs for navigating climate change.

Edmonton adopted a phased approach to develop its resilience strategy, unlike Calgary's single stage plan development process. In 2015, Edmonton first undertook scientific climate risk assessments to quantify infrastructure exposure and estimate potential economic losses from climate hazards through 2065. Knowledge gaps were identified for subsequent refinement. The findings were validated through external stakeholder workshops.

Building on this foundation, Edmonton then conducted multi-criteria economic analysis in 2017 to evaluate costs and benefits of various adaptation measures like enhanced stormwater management or expanded urban forests. Options analysis were conducted ensuring alignment with city goals and metrics like financial viability, co-benefit potential and flexibility, shaping viable resilience pathways.

In 2018, the draft resilience plan was opened for broader inputs through public engagement workshops, as well as thematic sessions focused on issues like public health, equity considerations and energy sector implications. Participation from community members, businesses, academics, and civil society helped incorporate diverse viewpoints into Edmonton's adaptation roadmap priorities and implementation approaches.

In all, a structured approach in climate risk assessment, economic analysis, followed by stakeholder engagement, enabled Edmonton to mobilise its climate adaptation strategy via scientific and economic rigour while also addressing community concerns and objectives.

More broadly, by pooling capacity and resources across states and provinces, collaborative initiatives aim to catalyse widespread equitable and economically viable local climate adaptation action, as exemplified by the Under2 Coalition between the state governments in Canada and the United States.

In 2017, the Under2 Coalition facilitated an inter-jurisdictional partnership between regional governments in the Great Lakes area encompassing 15 American states and the Canadian provinces of Ontario and Quebec. The participants pledged coordinated efforts on emissions mitigation and climate change adaptation by harnessing their collective capabilities. This led to collaborative pilot projects focused on climate modelling, risk analysis and testing shared green infrastructure solutions suitable for the ecosystem and climate of the broader region.

Specific problem areas being tackled in cross-boundary teams include extreme weather forecasting and early warning systems, cost-benefit analysis for resilience measures, as well as monitoring frameworks to track solution efficacy. The coalition has also established a common digital platform and technical toolbox for use by municipal and county-level administrators across the participating states and provinces. This features a repository of case studies, policy templates, outreach materials in local languages, and training programs - all aimed at building staff capabilities and technical capacity. There is also support extended to Indigenous communities around climate adaptation needs assessments and planning.

Over time, such collaborations between regional governments are expected to drive more consistent and coordinated adaptation strategies across issues like transportation networks, building codes, energy systems and housing. By pooling their strengths, they can boost climate resilience performance and contributions under local, state, and national commitments. The decentralised yet harmonised approach also enables course correction based on the lessons from various localised experiments while scaling programs that demonstrate robust evidence of success.

Indigenous Guardians programs that empower First Nations communities as stewards of their traditional lands have proliferated across Canada over the last decade. Close to 100 such programs are now active, spanning diverse regions from British Columbia to the Northwest Territories to southern Ontario. These provide a grassroots vehicle for Indigenous groups to apply their traditional knowledge and practices for conservation and sustaining their living assets.

The Mi'kmaq Confederacy of Prince Edward Island combines oral histories with scientific data to identify climate trends and vulnerable regions. It has prioritised coastal areas witnessing erosion and saltwater intrusion for community adaptation programs aimed at preserving cultural heritage sites and values against worsening storm surges. Such initiatives exemplify the power of interweaving Indigenous traditional wisdom with instrumental monitoring for building localised resilience.

In general, the Guardians undertake observation of environmental health, tracking climate impacts on sensitive ecosystems and endangered native species. This hyperlocal data allows them to detect signs of ecological change quicker than external researchers. They also educate youth and the wider public on sustainable practices while conducting habitat restoration and maintenance of protected conservation reserves. Planning economic development aligned to ecological limits of their ancestral lands is another key function.

Overall, Indigenous Guardians serve as the eyes, ears and voice for environmental stewardship grounded in Indigenous values. The networks of Guardians and their Indigenous knowledge systems thus complement scientific climate studies with on-ground insights and early warnings. Their autonomous management empowers self-determined climate resilience alongside preservation of culture and heritage. With adequate capacity building support, the Indigenous Guardians model is being emulated globally as a paradigm for inclusive, ethical, and locally relevant climate adaptation practice.

<u>Key Insights</u>	<u>Takeaway</u>
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(4) Market Development and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitate industry collaboration to drive solutions ● Identify shared challenges and collective opportunities ● Strengthen local supply chains and technology diffusion
(5) Finance and Affordability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop business cases demonstrating adaptation benefits ● Offer new financing solutions for technologies and resilience ● Enable the market conditions for success

Germany

LEAG, Germany's second-largest electricity producer, operated almost exclusively on lignite coal until the government decided in 2019 to phase out coal by 2038. Facing decline, LEAG plans to transform into a renewable energy leader with its GigawattFactory (GWF) initiative, spearheading the company's shift away from fossil fuels. GWF aims to invest up to €10 billion by 2030 to deliver green energy at scale, including large battery storage and electrolysis to produce hydrogen.

Transitioning a major electricity producer like LEAG from conventional fossil fuels to renewable energy involves monumental challenges. Specifically, without designing a profitable electricity market that makes large-scale renewable investments viable, managers and shareholders cannot commit billions to projects like GWF regardless of environmental goals. Additionally, constructing enough renewables capacity for GWF requires consent from multiple levels of government, adding political roadblocks. Finally, realising GWF's hydrogen plans depends on connecting to future hydrogen infrastructure in a timely manner. If the infrastructure arrives too late, LEAG cannot leverage hydrogen to full potential.

Overcoming these barriers requires major paradigm shifts from stakeholders used to a fossil fuel-focused business model. LEAG must convince partners, investors, customers, and governments that GWF represents feasible, relevant innovations worth cooperating on instead of 'business-as-usual'. If key players cling to old ways failing to embrace the sweeping systemic changes GWF represents, LEAG cannot lead the sustainability transformation it envisions. For GWF to spearhead LEAG's shift into a cutting-edge renewable leader, the company must align market forces, politics, infrastructure, and business partnerships behind common decarbonisation goals.

Japan

The newly launched Japan Climate Transition Bond Framework (CTBF) structurally embeds affordable decarbonisation through its innovative approach issuing sustainability and transition bonds for climate-aligned projects while dedicating a subset of proceeds to subsidise household distributed energy and efficiency upgrades.

The CTBF channels private capital to not only fund corporations’ and municipalities’ green development but to directly make renewable energy, building retrofits, EVs, and other technologies accessible for average families. The funding allocation linking corporate green underwriters and retail end-users accelerates fair energy transition. Issuing entities can receive upfront funding for their own net zero plans while driving an inclusive shift to clean power across Japan’s socioeconomic spectrum.

Blending dedicated pools of capital for both supply- and demand-side with targeted subsidies transforms the climate financing’s scope and scale. More importantly, it delivers equitable asset ownership and affordable access to carbon-free living essential for public buy-in. The integrated priorities within Japan’s bond framework provide a model for financing mechanisms globally to enable just, sustainable transitions benefitting all through strategic capital structuring.

Denmark

The City of Copenhagen 2025 Climate Plan’s specific actions are distributed across the four pillars: Energy Consumption, Energy Production, Mobility and City Administration Initiatives. Achieving the goal of carbon neutrality by 2025 will make Copenhagen a city with cleaner air, less noise, energy efficient dwellings and greener mobility.

Figure 6: Carbon emission reductions in Roadmap 2021-2025 across the four pillars of the CPH 2025 Climate plan (City of Copenhagen 2020)

Table 4: Overview of pillars, main action areas and initiatives in Roadmap 2021–2025 (City of Copenhagen 2020)

PILLAR	MAIN ACTIONS	INITIATIVES
<p>Energy Consumption</p> <p>The Energy Consumption in Roadmap 2021–2025 includes ten initiatives distributed across four main action areas, with a reduction of carbon emissions of 4,000 tonnes.</p>	<p>Energy-efficient operations</p>	Energy-efficient operation of district heating units
		Electricity savings
		Energy Leap partnering with professional building owners
		Social housing associations
		Property administrators - offers to cooperative and homeowner associations
	<p>Refurbishment and new build</p>	Energy retrofitting in the renewal of urban areas and buildings
		Energy-efficient focus in building permits
		Sustainability tool for local planning
	<p>Conversion</p>	Conversion of individually oil-heated buildings
	<p>Photovoltaic modules</p>	PV Action Plan
<p>Energy Production</p>		Continued securing of sustainable biomass

The Energy Production pillar in Roadmap 2021–2025 includes sixteen initiatives distributed across four main action areas, with a reduction of carbon emissions of 130,000 tonnes.

Carbon Neutral District Heating

Development of the future district-heat production

Development of the future district-heating system

Reducing the need for peak load production

Converting peak and reserve load capacity

Carbon Neutral Utilities

Green town gas

Development of district cooling

Carbon neutral water supplies and sewerage

Carbon-neutral waste-water processing

Wind and Sun

Establish onshore wind turbines

Establish offshore wind turbines

Establish large-scale PV systems

Resources and Waste

Establishing materials recovery facilities (Dirty MRF)

		Implementing biogas solution for organic household waste
		Higher level of household waste sorting
		Higher level of business/industry waste sorting
<p>Mobility</p> <p>The Mobility pillar in Roadmap 2021–2025 includes four initiatives distributed across three main areas that reduce total carbon emissions by 58,000 tonnes.</p>	Public transport	100% zero emission buses in 2025 (including harbour buses)
	Maritime traffic	Shore power for cruise ships
		Maritime environmental zone in Copenhagen’s inner basin
	Construction machinery	Conversion of non-road machinery in the city
<p>City Administration Initiatives</p> <p>The City Administration Initiatives pillar in Roadmap 2021–2025 includes seventeen initiatives distributed across six main action areas, with a reduction of carbon emissions of 8,000 tonnes.</p>	The city’s energy consumption	Energy retrofitting (energy efficiency projects)
		Energy-efficient operation (streamlining of day-to-day operations)
		Flexible energy consumption
		The City of Copenhagen’s new construction

	Street lighting
The city's transport	Efficient transport and electric and hydrogen powered vehicles
	Requirements for non-road mobile machinery in construction projects
	Tightened requirements for supplier transport
The city's companies	Charting of initiatives in the City of Copenhagen's companies
The city's procurement	Ecolabelled products and services
	Electricity-saving products
	Systematic follow-up
The city's woodlands	100,000 trees in Copenhagen
	Semi-urban tree planting
	Climate Ambassador Training Programme

	Training and information	Climate Action Showroom
		Climate Training Programme

Despite achieving an 80% reduction in emissions between 2009 and 2022, the city said it would not be able to complete the remaining 20% reduction through carbon capture and storage because of a critical piece of infrastructure’s failure (Christiansen & Hougaard 2022). Indeed, the Amager Resource Centre, a waste-to-energy plant, did not qualify for state financial aid for carbon capture projects. This funding, it argued, would otherwise have enabled them to capture CO₂ generated by burning the city’s waste. This has forced the Danish capital to push back plans to hit net zero by 2025. For investors, though, it has served as a reminder of how difficult the targets are to achieve (Langston 2022).

Zimbabwe

Bulawayo is the second largest city of Zimbabwe and has an urban population of between 680,000 and 1.5 million, according to official and unofficial estimates. The city showed rapid growth, like most African cities during the twentieth century; however, it slowed and reversed during the first decade of the twenty-first century due to substantial economic decline in the last years of the Mugabe Government. It is now growing again with a new emphasis on achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); hence, the case study is important for showing how cities can help reshape development around such issues as net-zero. The SDGs have been adopted as part of the Strategic Plan for Bulawayo, and the next steps involve finding opportunities for investment that can enable a future net-zero city:

- Leapfrogging toward sustainable development in the next economy: The idea in leapfrog development is jumping over existing technology to the next generation of technology when investing in new technology. The literature on leapfrogging suggests that this is possible if the cities and nations involved are able to create the kind of supportive governance base that can welcome and enable demonstrations and create partnerships for financing. The technologies relevant to leapfrogging Bulawayo into being a low- to net-zero emissions city include renewable power (especially solar with batteries), electromobility (especially new transit and micromobility), smart technologies that assist the grid and help reduce wastage of resources, and circular economy technologies for waste management.
- Bulawayo is looking to decommission the city’s old 90 MW thermal power station located in the CBD to build an equivalent sized solar power station on the outskirts of the city. As there is such a low power use at present it is possible for Bulawayo to be fully powered by solar within 3 to 5 years.

Korea

Seoul, the capital city of South Korea, has implemented a range of circular economy initiatives to reduce waste, promote sustainable production and consumption, and create a more resource-efficient city. Among other initiatives, the city of Seoul implemented:

- food waste recycling: Seoul has implemented a program to convert food waste into biogas, which is used to generate electricity and heat. The city has installed food waste collection systems in apartment buildings and other public facilities, and the collected waste is then transported to biogas plants for processing. This program has significantly reduced the amount of food waste sent to landfills and has helped to create a new source of renewable energy for the city;
- sharing economy platform: Seoul has launched a sharing economy platform called "ShareHub," which connects individuals and businesses to share resources and services. The platform includes a range of services, such as shared workspaces, tool libraries, and car-sharing services. By encouraging resource sharing, the platform helps to reduce waste and promote a more sustainable and resource-efficient city;
- upcycling: Seoul has implemented a program to upcycle waste materials into new products. The program includes initiatives such as "upcycling villages," where local artisans create new products from waste materials such as plastics, textiles, and metal. The upcycling program helps to reduce waste and promote sustainable production practices;
- circular economy education: Seoul has implemented a range of educational programs to raise awareness of the circular economy and promote sustainable production and consumption practices. These programs include workshops, seminars, and other educational events aimed at businesses, students, and the general public.

Overall, Seoul's circular economy initiatives demonstrate the city's commitment to creating a more sustainable and resource-efficient urban environment. The city is reducing waste by implementing programs such as food waste recycling, sharing economy platforms, and upcycling initiatives, promoting sustainable production and consumption, and creating a more resilient and sustainable city for its residents.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the theoretical underpinnings of net-zero carbon cities are multifaceted and dynamic, incorporating decarbonisation strategies across energy, transport, and the built environment. The emphasis on walkability, green space, social impacts, nature-based solutions, and resource recovery and reuse reflects a holistic approach to sustainable urban development and just transitions. As city planners, developers and dwellers continue the trend towards net-zero carbon emissions, a comprehensive theoretical framework that integrates technological advancements with human-centric design and community engagement will play a pivotal role in achieving this aim.

Leading cities pursuing ambitious emissions reductions goals are taking an inclusive, iterative approach to policy development and technological solutions. They leverage data and predictive modeling to track progress, amplify success stories, and integrate Indigenous knowledge. Industry collaboration through making the business case for adaptation and offering innovative financing drives technological and supply chain solutions to shared challenges, leading cities to drive progress towards their ambitious targets.

Please note: This is a live document based on the literature review and market scan. Recommendations will be added to the presentation pending feedback on the presentation and review.

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5th of March submission deadline. 4 assessors for each bid with limited time. They are generalists. Limited amount we can write. When they read it the framework needs to be clear. Needs to be

distilled and clear. Industry-led focus needs to be front and centre. Bring together what our approach is. Industry partners there. What we have to do is bring industries together in the bid. Need to make sure we've got sufficient info on what's actually going on. When we write the bid needs to be

Systems thinking being really used in cities across the world, but each city takes their own city to establish some sort of framing. Community led, governance-led,

Do we need to look at all of this and decide which is best for this mode. What's missing is our theory of change. How are we telling the stories of the collaboration we're forming will achieve desired change, do we need a framework above that.

All 3 city environments plans, transition plans, etc. Something to aim for that we don't have to create. Highlighting CE it drives towards plans. Saving grace in all of this in the AU setting.

State policies and targets, to see their incentives. NSW just updated theirs on tax and industry incentives. Diagram to see possibilities on the money end. Would be useful.

Sammy looked at business documents - 42 million as driver for industry-led NZC transition. What are cities doing to address funding gap.

Recommendations are fine. As much as we can put into this. Interested

Based on question:

1. What is the framework, process and methodology - is you can set governance model and missions then whole city can come around that. How they think change will be created. Mission-based Yara river, climate and policy. Utilising the framework to develop out. How do we bring this together. Not told in a story or a framework of how to do it.
2. AU - what is that we create - how to go from small innovation to scale up to CE. Basis of the way we've been looking at this. Go hand in hand. Developer looking at putting in a community battery. Should we do a pilot? Problem is you've only done one part of a bigger system. What they actually need is a full optimization at skill, what happens when EVs come in. Automation systems, efficient homes. Understanding this is important. Developer

worried about getting into retail that won't be. Pilots show a local impact but not a systems scale. All electric

3. Make Bradfield circular - end to end. What's that mean and different interventions we need with all the partners. Now it's housing challenge, what do they care about and put them into clusters that meet needs for all of them. So we don't have a bunch of individual projects. City environments at scale to pull ideas together.
4. Health precinct, knowledge precinct, Springfield Qld looking at a broader city building form the ground up. Victoria coming off gas. Regent Melbourne - wildly ambitious projects that are not sector specific. Need to think about finance and policy and not just jump to piloting. Lifting it up a level and then developing sub elements. Same framework for each area? They can be different in structuring - set the mission, pull industry partners around mission. Then build interventions around hairy ambitious targets. Look for unintended consequences. Set a big goal, get partners on board.

Got theories, then we need examples that would lead to theory of change. Challenge here is this goes into Dept of Industry and Science, they want to build AU industry. No partners have come with an EOI who have expressed that in cash. Got a resilience program, but no industry partners who are putting in funding for that. More focus on circular and digital.

6 - 10 have put in 100k interested in their products. Circular and digital. Group of networks, Green Buildign AU, green infrastructure, network partners. Smaller SME's who have new innovations, plan to have an incubator. Networks are other CE environments who wish to learn. Cash partners weigh heavily because they have cash in. Not sure about the scale.

Net Zero Act. <https://www.energy.nsw.gov.au/nsw-plans-and-progress/government-strategies-and-frameworks/climate-change-net-zero-future-act-2023>

Needs to be flexible and adaptable. Probably do want to first few project ideas on what they look like and can then refine them. Clear on how each of the big partners will work together.

Industry consultation - writing this as a meaningful sentence.

Excluded China for any reason?

Yesterday there was a post from environment and climate change canada - think we should focus on north america and canada - should focus on these two.